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AGRICULTURAL PROBLEMS OF THE POST-COLONIAL EAST: THE TEBHAGA MOVEMENT AND THE NATIONAL GOVERNMENT OF INDIA

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Abstract

The agrarian civilizations of the East were distinguished by a specific way of agriculture, a system of land-tax relations and state policy in solving peasant problems. The history of India, which was a British possession in South Asia for two hundred years, is filled with eventful events, among which some of the most striking, remaining in the memory of the Indian peoples, difficult for historical analysis, were the popular and peasant movements of different eras. The XIX-th and XX-th centuries, closest to us in time, provided examples of the Great Uprising of 1857–1859 (with the active participation of the peasantry, especially in the Principality of Oudh, where it became the main driving force), the “indigo uprising” on the indigo-bearing plantations of Bengal, the participation of peasants in the satyagrahas of Mahatma Gandhi in the 1920–1930s, the “August Revolution” of 1942, Telangana uprising that broke out in 1946 in Hyderabad. At the same time, the Tebhaga movement began in the east of India, which dealt a blow not only to the “outgoing” colonial regime, but also continued after India achieved independence.

Keywords: agrarian system of India, land tax systems, peasant castes, Tebhaga, policy of the national government.

I. INTRODUCTION

The subject of this article is the agrarian history of India, the Tebhaga movement of the second half of 1947–1949, which has not been sufficiently studied in modern domestic science. There are many reasons for this, but the main one is that this popular movement under the leadership of the Communist Party (CPI) was directed against the government of Jawaharlal Nehru, Home Minister Vallabhbhai Patel and, in general, against the leading party in the coalition cabinet – the Indian National Congress (INC). The appeal to the study of agrarian topics in the context of the communist movement after 1991 in our country lost its relevance, and a kind of ideological “blindsightedness in reverse” began to appear. And this is at a time when the problems of protest movements of very different nature and orientation, self-identification of strata of eastern and western, southern and northern societies (classes, confessions, ethnolinguistic groups, castes, professional clusters, etc.) have acquired unprecedented relevance in the world science (Private property in the East, 1988). The purpose of the article is to give a general description of the specifics of the agrarian structure of India and the Tebhaga movement at the stage of its development in independent India.

II. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

A feature of India's economic structure in the late 1940s and early 1950s, during its transition from colonial status to independence, was the multi-structured economy and its main industry – agriculture (Onischuk, 1995). Large and small private land ownership developed in the country, while the traditional socio-economic structure – the peasant community – was largely preserved. The features of the Indian peasant community in the northern, central and southern provinces and principalities of the country have been studied quite deeply by orientalists, primarily by L.B. Alaev (Alaev, Vigasin, Safronova, 2010; Alaev, 2016; 2018; 2019). Domestic researchers contributed to the understanding of agrarian problems and the specifics of eastern feudalism, the “Asian mode of production”, capitalism and the typology of societies in Asia and Africa: Yu.G. Alexandrov and B.I. Slavny (Alexandrov, Slavny, 1985, pp. 20-25), L.S. Vasiliev (Vasiliev, 1988, pp. 65-75), O.E. Nepomnin and N.A. Ivanov (Nepomnin, Ivanov, 2010), S.V. Onischuk (Onischuk, 1995) and others. From an objective-critical position, the authors analyze complex phenomena and show the specifics of Indian agrarian civilization.

Among the Indian authors who worked on the stated plot are the names of S. Bandyopadhyay (Bandyopadhyay, 2009), V. Bhagwan (Bhagwan, 1971), M.L. Bhargava (Bhargava, 1987), J. Biswas (Biswas, 2002), who assessed the progressive and destructive aspects of peasant armed uprisings. Agrarian issues in the refraction of the biographies of the largest Indian politicians of the period under study are presented in the works of Indians: P.N. Chopra (Chopra, 1995), K.D. Gangrate (Gangrate, 2004, p. 212-223). In Anglo-American historiography, the Tebhaga can be found in the general works of R.P. Dutt (Dutt, 1948), M. Brecher (Brecher, 1959), J. Brown (2003), J. Darwin (Darwin, 1988), P. Moon (1968), B. Zacharia (Zacharia, 2004). What is common in their approaches is the desire to show the futility of the protest movement of the weakly organized peasant stratum and the influence of communist propaganda on the formation of anti-state protest “surges”. A detailed study of the agrarian system of colonial and post-colonial India in direct connection with the Tebhaga movement still awaits its author.

Under the British colonial rule, almost immediately after the conquest of the first territories in the northeast of India, agrarian reforms began, with the goal of intensifying agricultural production through the development of the capitalist structure in the Indian village, the “removal” of large private landowners oriented towards market production and the creation of a wide a layer of small private owners who will also run their farms profitably and contribute to the formation of the Indian version of the farmer's path to the development of capitalism. L.B. Alaev points out that initially the British thought that “the task is very simple - to adopt their taxation system from the previous masters, maintain the previous tax rates and the previous apparatus and appropriate the previous income of the maharajas and nawabs (i.e. Indian princes. – L. Ch.) (Alaev, 2019, p. 222).

It turned out that in reality everything was much more complicated. The Indians paid taxes not only in cash, but also through a flexible system of transferring money into goods and products, which did not suit the British. In addition, the colonialists disbanded the previous local armies, broke the former, albeit fragmented, statehood, and dealt a blow to the traditional peasant community, the city, which lived largely due to the service of princely squads and a developed system of services. The community survived, but it was subjected to severe deformation, which led to a sharp reduction in cultivated areas (even in places that were the real breadbasket of Hindustan before colonization – for example, in Bengal), cases of mass famine and, as a result, an increase in epidemiological danger. The reduction in the urban population of an essentially medieval Indian city entailed another extreme - a sharp drop in prices for agricultural products, and the cash tax became a completely unbearable burden for the villagers. The tax farming system did not solve, but rather aggravated the problem (Vasiliev, 1988, pp. 67-70).

The subject of this article focuses specifically on Bengali issues. In search of effective methods for developing the agricultural sector of the economy, the colonial authorities, represented by Viceroy Cornwallis, introduced a special land tax system in the east of India at the end of the 18th century - in other parts of the colony there were three specific land tax systems.

Bengal was called "permanent zamindari", or permanent taxation. Its essence was that the main object of taxation was the large Hindu landowner - the zamindar. According to Cornwallis, the Indian zamindar was supposed to turn into an analogue of a land lord, caring about the profitability of his farm and the profitability of agricultural production. Bengal, from the point of view of the presence of natural resources in it, was unique. The great Ganges flows through its territory, with its tributaries, forming vast expanses of well-moistened fertile soil. In addition, the region had flat fields on which, since ancient times, all types of cereals, fruits and vegetables, and indigo-bearing shrubs were grown (to produce the blue-black natural dye that was in demand throughout the Asian East). In addition to agriculture, fishing, weaving and many other traditional activities characteristic of agrarian civilization developed.

The British believed that by establishing a permanent tax on the Zamindars, they would stimulate them – the future "land lords" – of Bengal to increase the intensification of production and develop new agricultural areas. However, the constant land tax rate, equal to 90% of the previous one, did not provide the desired result. First of all, the factor of difference in mentality and tradition of Indian large landowners and the British new nobles came into force. The zamindars were not interested in intensifying production, optimizing costs and limiting the usual luxurious lifestyle (Alexandrov, Slavny, 1985, p. 20-25). The utilitarian idea of the British – to "create" the landlord from Bengal zamindars – turned out to be a failure, moreover, it led to catastrophic consequences: destruction of the way of life, ruin, famine. And it was the amateur population of the region who suffered most of all, who served the land holdings of the zamindars as tenants or subtenants, i.e. - various categories of Indian peasantry. By the middle of the 20th century, Bengal, as a province of British India, had not fully overcome the impact of experiments with land tax systems.

"Tebhaga" literally means "third part" in Bengali. This word in the Indian and world historical science refers to the movement of peasant sharecroppers (bargadars, adhyars) in Bengal in 1946–1949 (until August 15, 1947 in British India, then until 1949 in independent India and East Pakistan) for reducing rent to 1/3 of the harvest. Tenant peasants (bargadars and adhyars) of the provinces of West Bengal and Assam traditionally gave half of their hard-earned crops to landowners (zamindars, jotedars). At first, the Tebhaga participants put forward the slogan of giving only a third of the harvest to the landowner, and keeping two thirds for themselves, but as they developed, especially in the post-colonial period, they began to pursue broader goals: abolition of the zamindari system without compensation; transfer of land to those who cultivate it, which reflected the aspirations of a large part of the poor peasantry.

The Communist Party of India, created in 1925, was a vehicle for the ideas of world revolution and acted with the support of the Communist International (until its dissolution in 1943). On the eve of the historical phenomenon we are studying, in July 1946, the CPI adopted a resolution calling on Indians to the revolutionary struggle, and specifically the peasantry to participate in it together with the working class (Documents of the History of the Communist Party of India, 1976, p. 124 -125). Thus, the CPI became the first party in the history of the country that set itself the goal of mobilizing the peasantry as a class for a people's democratic revolution and overthrowing the power of the bourgeois Congress government led by Jawaharlal Nehru (Documents of the History of the Communist Party of India, 1976, p. 128-130). The leadership of the Bengal Provincial Peasant Union, inspired by the communists, called upon the peasants to move under the slogan "Tebhaga".

The movement has spread to the most inaccessible areas of West Bengal, such as Sundarbans in District 24 Parganas, Domjur and Jagatballavpur in Howrah, Bora Kamalapur and Chanditala in Hooghly, Jaipur and Vishnupur districts in Bankura, and many other localities covered with the Tebhaga and the neighboring province of Assam (Proceedings of the Assam Legislative Assembly, 12th March, 1948; Bandyopadhyay, 2009, p. 116). The peasants resorted to a wide variety of methods of struggle. From the police report, information can be extracted about specific examples illustrating the tebhaga in action. Thus, in Hooghly there were clashes with zamindars and local Congress leaders, arson of houses and barns of landowners, sabotage and armed attacks on large landowners. The Minister of Home Affairs of the Government of India, Vallabhbhai Patel, ordered a decisive suppression of the spread of peasant protests. Bengal Home Minister Kiran Shankar Roy, following instructions from above, stated in the provincial legislative assembly that "in these areas (meaning the above-mentioned areas. – L. Ch.) the communists have been in power for more than six months.

On February 22, 1948, a group of 400–500 people, with communist slogans, attacked the house of one of the Congressists, all members of his family were killed... Some administrative buildings and the local library were also burned. On March 10 and 11, 1948, in the village of Kamalpur, several houses of Congressists were again attacked and destroyed by members of the movement" (Weekly Confidential Report Ending 29th November, 1948). Documents indicate that when the local police intervened in the case and arrested 4 communists, "a huge crowd of people, men and women, armed with improvised means and even Taoists (large knives with a one-sided straight blade. – L. Ch.) tried recapture those arrested. The police, after several warnings, opened fire and killed the two attackers" (Weekly Confidential Report Ending 29th November, 1948). On January 22, 1949, similar incidents occurred in the Hooghly district and other places.

By order of Patel, who sought to stop the growth of the protest movement into the neighboring provinces of the country, the Bengal Tebhaga movement was not always made public and was almost not reflected in the press and other media. For many months, many villages and towns in West Bengal remained essentially outside the control of the central and provincial authorities (NAI. Ministry of Home Affairs. 1949. Branch Police I. File No. 12/A. L. 5-9). The communists filled this vacuum. Due to numerous complaints from the jotedars in May 1949, no new methods of collecting taxes from peasants or managing agricultural work had yet been applied, which led to disruption of the rhythm of the peasant season and even disruption of the harvest. The normal work of the farmers could resume only when the demands of the communists were met: the landowner had to accept the demands of the participants in the tebhaga, join the ranks of the party and pay all taxes and fulfill other instructions. Nothing of the kind happened, and attacks on landowners' estates continued.

Thus, in Midnapore, about 600 people were arrested on charges of similar crimes in the Tamluk settlement alone by April 1949, but these repressions did not stop the further development of peasant uprisings. From the spring of 1949 to January 1950, more than 17 cases of armed uprisings by peasants under the leadership of the CPI occurred in the settlements of Garbeta, Panskura, Daspur, Tamluk, and Chandrokona (NAI. Ministry of Home Affairs. 1949. Branch Police I. File No. 12/A. L. 10-11, 23; Biswas, 2002, pp. 96-97, 111). In December 1949, in the Rajshahi district, on the banks of the Ganges, the peasants of Nachole rebelled under the leadership of the communists. The villages of Ghasura, Chandipur, Kendua, Rautara, Jagdai, Dharol, Shyampura and Napitpara refused to pay rent to landowners and resorted to violence. Local landowners often fled for their lives. The peasants declared the areas liberated from the power of the landowners "tebhaga elaka" and at general meetings elected their authorities – the "tebhaga committees", announced the complete liquidation of landownership.

On the personal instructions of Vallabhai Patel, the provincial authorities sent military units and police detachments to suppress the movement; there was a real war between peasant detachments and punitive forces, who were supported by mercenary detachments formed by the zamindar landowners. Among the prominent figures of the Tebhaga movement, according to historical documents, there were many women whose names remained in the annals of peasant struggle: Rani Mitra Dasgupta, Manikuntala Sen, Renu Chakravarty and Bimala Majhi. A women's battalion "Naribahini" was even created, and the heroine leader of the Tebhaga was the widow Bimala Majhi, who, when arrested, was charged with committing 140 "crimes". Only large punitive forces arrived at the beginning of 1950 and suppressed the uprising. Repression and arrests spread throughout Bengal and Assam, and at least 30 local Tebhaga leaders, men and women, were imprisoned (NAI. Ministry of Home Affairs. 1949. Branch Police I. File №. 12/A. L. 16–17). Thus the movement stopped.

III. CONCLUSION

Along with the military advantage of the authorities, to a large extent the reasons for the suppression of the Tebhaga in independent India were of an "organizational" nature. In contrast to the communist uprisings of 1948–1949 in China, Malaya and Vietnam, the weakness of the Indian movements was their inability to reach all of peasant, rural India. It remained based on the base of the rural marginal element, the tribes, the poorest sections. Also, compared to the Tebhaga in its early development under the colonial regime in British India (1946), the peasant movements in West Bengal under the Nehru government did not have a single goal, a single demand.

For the majority of participants in this struggle, the slogans of the CPI regarding the accomplishment of the people's democratic revolution were distant and incomprehensible. A unified leadership from the CPI, educated bhadralok (Bengali Brahmins and scribes – literally “noble”. – L.Ch.) generated ideas, but the real command on the ground was exercised by little-known people from the peasant environment, whose strategy and tactics were simply impossible to predict. What can be certain is that they were far from the complexities of the ideology of the urban elite.

However, the stubborn struggle of the peasants still led to a constructive result: the then government of Bengal was forced to make a concession – to legally limit the rent to landowners to one third of the harvest. The special Act of 1950 recognized peasants as the owners of their land. The Tebhaga became one of the most powerful armed protest movements in post-colonial India under Nehru and Patel, which showed a complex system of socio-economic and political contradictions of post-colonial society on its path to the formation of a sovereign self-sufficient economy (while maintaining large private property) and political sovereignty, the formation of a democratic republic. The combination of forceful methods of suppressing mass protests and the application of social reforms helped lower the threshold of conflict and ensured fairly long periods of stability in Indian society.

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АГРАРНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПОСТКОЛОНИАЛЬНОГО ВОСТОКА: ДВИЖЕНИЕ ТЕБХАГА И НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ПРАВИТЕЛЬСТВО ИНДИИ

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Аннотация

Аграрные цивилизации Востока отличались специфическим укладом сельского хозяйства, системы земельно-налоговых отношений и политики государства в решении крестьянских проблем. История Индии, двести лет бывшей британским владением в Южной Азии, наполнена насыщенными событиями, среди которых одними из самых ярких, оставшихся в памяти индийских народов, сложных для исторического анализа, явились народные, крестьянские движения разных эпох. Самые близкие нам по времени, XIX и XX века дали примеры Великого восстания 1857–1859 г. (с активным участием крестьянства, особенно в княжестве Ауд, где оно стало главной движущей силой), «восстания индиго» на индигоносных плантациях Бенгалии, участия крестьян в сатьяграхах Махатмы Ганди в 1920–1930-х гг., «Августовской революции» 1942 г., в Теланганском восстании, вспыхнувшем в 1946 г. в Хайдарабаде. Тогда же на востоке Индии началось движение тебхага, которое нанесло удар не только по «уходящему» колониальному режиму, но и продлилось после достижения Индией независимости.

Ключевые слова: аграрный строй Индии, земельно-налоговые системы, крестьянские касты, тебхага, политика национального правительства.

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